

The Effect of Leading Style on the Working Motivation of Officials at the People's Committee of Ba Ria - Vung Tau Province's

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ABSTRACT: The People's Committee of Ba Ria-Vung Tau province has about 1500 staff members working, of which the Office of the Provincial People's Committee is 100 people, 23 departments under the Provincial People's Committee are about 1400 people. Over the years, the province's socio-economic development has developed rapidly and sustainably, achieving many encouraging achievements. However, there are still some issues that are not positive, in which a part comes from a part of the cadres and civil servants. Through the survey of public officials of the Office of the Provincial People's Committee and 23 departments under the People's Committee of Ba Ria-Vung Tau province with 26 independent and dependent variables, the author analyzes and evaluates positive and negative impacts of each leadership style to the working motivation of public servants, thereby reaching conclusions and implicating the management of the necessary elements to create the best work motivation for the staff.

KEYWORDS: Leading style, Working motivation

1. INTRODUCTION

Ba Ria - Vung Tau province is a large province in the southern region, with many industrial parks, often dealing with large workloads and high requirements for quality and progress. Therefore, Ba Ria - Vung Tau needs a team of cadres and civil servants who are professional, dynamic, creative, enthusiastic and dedicated to meeting the requirements of the development of Ba Ria - Vung Tau. Therefore, Ba Ria - Vung Tau has always been one of the leading localities in the country in attracting quality human resources to work in state agencies. However, an ongoing situation in some localities in the province is that the current contingent of cadres and civil servants is not dedicated, dedicated, promoting their sense of responsibility and passion for their work. Has a depressed mentality and does not want to stick with the work they are undertaking, significantly affecting the effectiveness and efficiency of state management in the locality; this is the source of the negative manifestations. The status of officials and civil servants at the People's Committee working moderately with a shared sense of responsibility is showing widespread signs. Many civil servants are not wholeheartedly and wholeheartedly devoted, have not actively studied, improved their knowledge and professional ethics, improved their professional qualifications and responded to work tasks in the development stage. Ba Ria - Vung Tau province is facing the increasing requirements of international integration today.

Although, with the attention of the whole political system in Ba Ria - Vung Tau province, along with many policies to encourage and encourage, cadres and civil servants can put their best efforts into their work wholeheartedly. However, the actual effect has not been achieved as expected, so there needs to be a specific study on the impact of leadership style on the working motivation of civil servants at the People's Committee of Ba Ria province - Vung Tau today to have comprehensive solutions, to create a highly effective functional incentive for the staff to encourage and motivate the passion and efforts in the work of the employees to be able to bring about the expected results, further improve the effectiveness and efficiency in state management, the quality of public services, and contribute to the development of Ba Ria - Vung Tau province.

The relationship between leaders and employees directly under them is significant and profoundly affects the success of leadership, administration and management. The study of the impact of leadership styles on the working motivation of civil servants at the People's Committee of Ba Ria - Vung Tau province. For the above reasons, the author has selected the topic "The influence of leadership style on the working motivation of civil servants at the People's Committee of Ba Ria - Vung Tau Province", is necessary to implement.

2. THEORETICAL BASIS AND RESEARCH MODEL

2.1. Leadership style

Many studies suggest several different leadership styles: authoritarian leadership style, democratic leadership style, liberal leadership style, transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style, and transactional leadership style, Situational leadership style, bureaucratic leadership style, charismatic leadership style. According to recent studies (Rachelle, 2015, Sakiru et al., 2013), leadership styles are generally divided by researchers into four (04) basic types:

(1) Autocratic leadership style: The leader assigns tasks and directs employees to perform those tasks without listening to employees' opinions.

(2) Democratic leadership style (democratic). Leaders discuss and agree in the decision-making process, and the leader will usually be the one to make the final decision on behalf of the leadership.

(3) Liberal leadership style: good leaders allow employees to make their own decisions but are ultimately responsible.

(4) Transformational Leadership: A process in which leaders inspire and stimulate subordinates to achieve better-than-expected results by understanding and eliciting higher-order needs, building trust with them, and always putting the organisations' interests above their own (Avolio et al., 1991; Rachelle, 2015).

2.2. Motivation to work

Herzberg (1959) divides motivation into internal and external groups; employees are motivated to perform behaviours to satisfy their needs: achievement, affiliation, and energy. In the same opinion,

Pinder (1998) believes that work motivation is a set of work energy from inside and outside of an individual related to work performance. However, both authors have not mentioned the difference between these two groups of factors according to the personal characteristics of employees or occupations.

Carl Rogers (1995) believes that the source of motivating people to act comes from within people, such as innate performance tendencies, self-actualizations need, or self-actualizations needs. This means that the motivation that drives people to perform is intrinsic to realising their abilities to make them more mature (Following, H.L. Petri & J.M. Govern, 2004). This research is limited when it says that people's needs are inherent in nature and ignore the changes in their needs during work and social interaction.

Sharing the same view that motivation comes from needs, the authors Leonchiev (1989) and Vygotsky (2014) said that, when considering the issue of encouragement, human reason must be regarded as in the relationship. with need. Human work motivation comes from requirements and has a close relationship with needs. Therefore, when studying human work motivation, it is necessary to explore people's relationship with factors in the environment of human activities. Deci and Ryan (1991) also argue that one of the primary determinants of motivation is their need for a particular social context. If people perceive that their demand is not being met, they will engage in behaviours that lead to satisfying that need. Although these studies have shown that the needs and motivations of people to work must be associated with specific working environments and conditions, they are not related to specific personal characteristics and professions.

2.3. Research models

Leadership style and work motivation are closely related. Leadership style affects employees' job satisfaction and has a significant role in organisational and social behaviour (Bahadori, 2012). Yousef (2000) pointed out that ethical conduct has a positive relationship with employee job satisfaction because managers must apply leadership styles to suit the working environment and improve high employee satisfaction.

Sakiru et al. (2013) showed that transformational and transactional leadership styles have meaningful relationships with the job satisfaction of employees of small and medium enterprises in Nigeria. Still, leadership style Professional leadership makes employees more satisfied. Al-Ababneh & Lookwood (2010) found a significant difference in the impact of three leadership styles: authoritarian, democratic and liberal on employee satisfaction in the Jordan compound, in which they were satisfied with the people's leadership style of managers. Bhatti et al. (2012) show that teachers at Lahore schools are delighted with the democratic style and are not satisfied with the unique leadership style of the school principal. Metvally et al. (2014) showed that conversion ethics positively impacts employees' job satisfaction in multinational companies in Egypt. Wangithi (2014) surveyed 844 teachers at high schools in Northern Kaiiado in Kenya; the results showed that most of the staff were dissatisfied with the principal's authoritarian

leadership style, while the healthy type of Democratic leadership, liberal leadership style and transformational leadership style positively affect employee satisfaction.

Figure 1. Research model

- Hypothesis H1: The democratic leadership style positively influences the working motivation of civil servants at the People's Committee of Ba Ria - Vung Tau province.
- Hypothesis H2: Transformational leadership style positively affects the working motivation of civil servants at the People's Committee of Ba Ria - Vung Tau province.
- Hypothesis H3: Liberal leadership style positively affects the working motivation of civil servants at the People's Committee of Ba Ria - Vung Tau province.
- Hypothesis H4: The authoritarian leadership style has a negative effect on the working motivation of civil servants at the People's Committee of Ba Ria - Vung Tau province.

3. METHODS

The research sample is selected by the non-probability method, namely the convenient sampling method, which is acceptable to save time.

According to some studies, the representativeness of the number of samples selected for the survey will be appropriate if the sample size is five samples for an estimate (Bollen 1989), the survey model in the thesis is expected to include four independent factors set up with 21 observed variables. Therefore, the required number of samples is $21 \times 5 = 105$ samples or more. So the number of samples used in the survey is $n=300$, so the sample's representativeness is guaranteed for the study.

After completing the collection, the survey tables will be reviewed to remove unsatisfactory surveys, then coded, inputted, and cleaned using SPSS software. The author uses Cronbach's Alpha tool to assess the reliability of the scale measuring the influence of leadership style on the work motivation of civil servants at the People's Committee of Ba Ria - Vung Tau province, eliminating the Unsuitable variables and conducting EFA analysis for suitable variables, if successful, these variables will continue to be included in regression analysis to test the correlation between the variables and test the fit of the model.

Data collection will be done by distributing questionnaires at the People's Committee of Ba Ria - Vung Tau province. The questionnaire was built as concisely and concisely as possible to ensure that it would not take much time for the respondents and

collect the maximum number of answer sheets. Data collectors are also trained in the necessary skills to manage effectively, such as Reading and recording information, interviewing skills, persuasion skills, and listening skills.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Research sample

The total number of questionnaires distributed was 300, surveying cadres and civil servants working at the People's Committee of Ba Ria - Vung Tau province... The total number of questionnaires collected was 297. After checking, there were 13 unsatisfactory votes will be disqualified (due to incomplete answer information). Thus, the total number of analysed and processed questionnaires is 284 with complete answer options.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics results

	Frequency	(%)
Gender		
Male	155	54,6%
Female	129	45,4%
Age		
Under 25 years old	17	6,0%
25-35 years old	78	27,5%
From 35-45 years old	138	48,6%
Over 45 years old	51	18,0%
academic level		
College	20	7,0%
University	225	79,2%
Post-Graduate	39	13,7%
WORKING TIME		
Less than five years	27	9,5%
From 5-10 years	127	44,7%
10-20 years	79	27,8%
Over 20 years	51	18,0
Total	284	100,0%

4.2. Multivariable linear regression results

The coefficient of determination R2 (R square) is used to evaluate the fit of the research model. The coefficient of determination R2 has been shown to not decrease with the number of independent variables included in the model; however, it has also been shown that it is not true that the more variables an equation fits the data better. Thus, R2 tends to be an optimistic estimator of the model fit measure for data with more than one explanatory variable in the model

Table 2. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	SE	Durbin-Watson
1	.740a	.547	.541	.26100	1.680
a. Predictors: (Constant), TD, CD, DC, DD					
b. Dependent Variable: DL					

The adjusted R2 value of 0.541 shows that the independent variable included in the regression affects 54.1% of the change of the dependent variable; the remaining 45.9% is due to variables outside the model and random error.

Durbin – Watson coefficient = 1,680, in the range of 1.5 to 2.0, so there is no first-order sequence autocorrelation.

Table 3. ANOVA

Model		Sum of squares	df	Mean squares	F	Sig.
1	Regression	22.991	4	5.748	84.378	0.000b
	Residuals	19.005	279	.068		
	Total	41.996	283			

Table 3 shows the results of multiple regression and the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable based on partial regression coefficient B, beta coefficient and partial and partial correlation coefficient.

Sig F-test is equal to 0.00 < 0.05, so the multiple linear regression model fits the data set and can be used.

Table 4. Regression results

Model		Unstandardised coefficient		Standardised coefficients	t	Sig.	Multicollinearity	
		B	SE	Beta				VIF
1	(Constant)	.505	.202		2.497	.013		
	CD	.259	.022	.478	11.825	.000	.994	1.006
	DC	.226	.021	.442	10.936	.000	.991	1.009
	DD	.177	.031	.233	5.750	.000	.987	1.013
	TD	.181	.031	.239	5.889	.000	.988	1.012

a. Dependent Variable: DL

Sig test t-regression coefficients of the independent variables are all less than 0.05, so the independent variables are significant to explain the dependent variable; no variable is excluded from the model.

The VIF coefficients of the independent variables are all less than 2, so there is no multicollinearity.

The results show that most of the regression coefficients have positive values, and the influence of the variables on the variable DL is statistically significant (sig < 0.05). Thus, the independent factors have the same impact on the dependent element, "Work motivation".

Regression model:

$$DL = 0.505 + 0.478*CD + 0.442*DC + 0.233*DD + 0.239*TD$$

Through the regression model, we can see that the leadership style factors influence the working motivation of civil servants at the People's Committee of Ba Ria - Vung Tau province.

5. CONCLUSION

The study used a convenient sampling method; 270 questionnaires met data analysis and processing requirements. After evaluating the reliability of Cronbach's alpha and analysing the EFA exploratory factors, four factors were drawn as the proposed model. The regression model is suitable; the independent variables explain about 54.1% of the variation of the dependent variable. All statistical hypotheses are accepted. The independent variables all have the same effect on the dependent variable.

The test shows no difference in the working motivation of cadres and civil servants of Ba Ria - Vung Tau Province People's Committee according to individual characteristics: gender, age, qualifications, and working time. The decreasing degree of factors affecting job satisfaction of cadres and civil servants of Ba Ria - Vung Tau Province People's Committee, respectively, is as follows: transformational leadership style, factors of democratic leadership style, and style of leadership style. Liberal leadership, authoritarian leadership style.

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